

Frontline Clinical Diagnosis – FTIR on Pancreatic Cancer

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Abstract. Accurate, easily accessible and economically viable cancer diagnostic tools are pivotal in improving the abysmal 5% survival rate of pancreatic cancer. Diagnosis accuracy as high as 90% has been achieved using a novel, affordable, non-invasive diagnostic method by combining measurement precision of infra-red spectroscopy with classification using machine learning tools. The study investigated urine and blood from pancreas cancer patients and healthy volunteers, and significantly improved accuracy by focusing on sweet-spots within blood plasma fractions containing molecules within a narrow range of molecular-weights. We introduce a novel approach leveraging a unique machine learning pipeline comprising class-specific principal component analysis (PCA), linear discriminant analysis (LDA), and support vector machine (SVM) in both real patient and synthetic data. By conducting separate PCA on cancerous and non-cancerous samples and integrating the projections prior to LDA and SVM classification, we demonstrate significantly improved diagnostic accuracy compared to traditional methods¹. This methodology not only enhances predictive performance but also offers deeper insights into the influence of molecular spectra on model efficacy. In addition, we incorporate MLA-WGAN (Multi-head Latent Attention Wasserstein Generative Adversarial Network), which successfully generates diverse, realistic spectra that maintain diagnostically relevant features while introducing meaningful training data variety, demonstrating critical capabilities for small spectral datasets. Our findings, validated on real patient data, suggest a promising avenue for developing non-invasive, accurate diagnostic tools for early-stage pancreatic cancer detection.

Keywords: Infrared spectroscopy, machine learning, pancreatic cancer

Fig. 1. Summary of cancer diagnostic techniques. Highlighted by circles, Pancreatic cancer work (shown as ■) and oral cancer work (shown as ▲) on plasma is from our research group on 74 pancreatic and 120 oral cancer patients². Raman data is also from our own research on 90 patients' serum, though the 10-30kDa variation is on an 18-patient subset. Head/Neck/Brain cancer data from a recent study by Van Der Hoorn et al.³ using 854 patients for the MRI and 287 for the apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) imaging metric and clinical validation results from an IR brain cancer study by Butler et al.⁴ (shown as ●). Mammogram (MG) combined with clinical examination (CBE) were from a breast cancer (shown as ◆) study on 32,080 patients by Noriaki et al.⁵ The dotted curve represents a qualitative boundary of acceptability followed by us with a minimum 85% accuracy. Accuracy is defined as the % of cases classified correctly.

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